

Nama Hottentot

also known as “Khoi”

Data source: eHRAF

Secondary source

Entered by Emily Pitek, Human Relations Area Files

** Data Source entry, prepared based on data sourced from an external project.*

** Secondary Source entry, prepared from a literature review by a Ph.D. RA*

Entry tags: African Religions, Religious Group

“Hottentot” is the name that early European travelers (primarily the 17th century Dutch) gave to the indigenous herders of southern Africa, and “Nama” refers to a sub-division of the group. “Khoi” is the preferred name, and means “the real people”. The first European settlers arrived in the Khoi’s region of southern Africa (the Cape of Good Hope region) in the mid-17th century, and quickly displaced the Khoi to more remote, arid lands. In the 18th century, the Khoi population rapidly declined as a result of warfare, smallpox epidemics, intermarriage with other groups, and integration into settler society. This entry places a focus on the Gei//Khauan tribe around the time of 1860, and relies on ethnographic information that describes the remaining traditional beliefs/practices. The Khoi traditionally lived in tribal communities comprised of several patrilineal clans. One of these clans claimed seniority, and the chieftainship was hereditary within this senior clan. The tribal community was led by the chief and a council of older men. Together, the chief and the council served as the judicial council and controlled matters of communal importance such as feasts, sacrifices, and pasture land relocations. The Khoi’s pastoralist-based subsistence economy required that communities be mobile in order to provide enough food and water to their herds. Information on traditional Khoi religious beliefs and practices for the time this entry focuses on is limited as, “Khoi have been under missionary influence for a considerable length of time, and relatively little information regarding religious beliefs is available” (Boonzaier, 2010). Although not described in substantial ethnographic detail, supernatural beings are identified as being present. The most important of these beings include Haitsiabena, a deified folk-hero, and ghosts of the dead (called /hei/nun, /hei khoin, sobo khoin, or //gaunagu). The /hei/nun do not appear to have been regularly invoked through organized family or tribal ancestor worship. Khoi rituals/ceremonies centered around life-cycle events and the transition from one status to another, emphasizing the times of birth, puberty, adulthood, marriage, and death. During these rituals the concept of !nau is important; !nau is a state of vulnerability/danger that the individual experiences, and is associated with social seclusion and some food taboos. Among the Khoi, a magician/diviner (!gai aob) is a respected and important person within the community. The !gai aob cures people who have been bewitched, and is possibly connected with some religious rites. Although the !gai aob is a respected and important person in the community, he does not appear to be a full-time specialist religious practitioner. For the Khoi, religion is interwoven throughout many aspects of society. Consequently, this entry considers the religious group to be coterminous with society itself.

Date Range: 1855 CE - 1900 CE

Region: Southwestern Africa, ca. 1860

Region tags: Africa, Southern Africa, Namibia, South Africa

Southwestern Africa (Namibia and South Africa), ca. 1860 (with specific focus on the Gei//Khauan tribe).

Status of Participants:

- ✓ Elite
- ✓ Religious Specialists
- ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Tuden, A. & Marshall, C. (Oct., 1972). Political organization: Cross-cultural codes 4. *Ethnology*, 11(4), 436-464.
- Source 2: Murdock, G.P. & Wilson, S.F. (Jul., 1972). Settlement patterns and community organization: Cross-Cultural Codes 3. *Ethnology*, 11(3), 254-295.
- Source 3: Divale, W. 2004. Codebook of Variables for the Standard Cross-Cultural Sample. *World Cultures: The Journal of Cross-Cultural and Comparative Research*.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=fx13-015>
- Source 1 Description: Schapera, Isaac. 1930. "Culture Of The Hottentots." *Khoisan Peoples Of South Africa; Bushmen And Hottentots*, By I. Schapera. London: G. Routledge.
- Source 2 URL: <https://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=fx13-001>
- Source 2 Description: Schultze, Leonhard Sigmund, Elizabeth C. Knight, and Theodore Ziolkowski. 1907. "In Namaland And The Kalahari." Jena: Gustav Fischer.
- Source 3 URL: <https://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=fx13-000>
- Source 3 Description: Boonzaier, Emile. 2010. "Culture Summary: Khoi." New Haven, Conn.: Human Relations Area Files.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: "All the Hottentot tribes have for a considerable time been more or less under the influence of missionaries. As a result their traditional religion has fallen largely, if not completely, into decay, and the great majority of the people in fact now claim to be Christians. The reports available about their religious beliefs and practices at the time when they first came in contact with Europeans are very inadequate; but even the later writers, although adding considerably to our knowledge, have, with the exception of Hahn, made little attempt to inquire more systematically into the subject. It is perhaps hardly possible, therefore, to arrive at anything like a full conception of the original religious cult of the Hottentots" (Schapera, 1930:374).

Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Yes

Notes: SCCS Variable 1649, Frequency of Internal Warfare (Resolved Rating), indicates that internal warfare seems to occur almost constantly and at any time of the year (Ember and Ember, 1992; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– Yes

Notes: SCCS Variable 1650, Frequency of External Warfare (Resolved Rating), indicates that internal warfare seems to occur almost constantly and at any time of the year (Ember and Ember, 1992; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating that the Khoi would actively proselytize and recruit new members.

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Notes: The Khoi religious group is coterminous with the Khoi society. Because of this, the religion is considered to have official political support.

↳ Are the priests paid by polity:

– No

Notes: "Some individuals played a dominant role in healing or rainmaking rituals, but it would be incorrect to view them as specialist religious practitioners. There is some mention of magicians, but very little is known of the methods they employed" (Boonzaier, 2010).

↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:

– No

Notes: Religious infrastructure is not present. According to Murdock and Wilson (1972; Column 6: Large or Impressive Structures), "there are no structures in the community that are appreciably larger or more impressive than the usual residential dwellings."

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– I don't know

Notes: "It appears from the clan names of the Gei //Khauan [tribe] that there must formerly have been several more clans in this tribe, so that on the whole the size of a clan cannot have been considerable. No actual figures are available, however" (Schapera, 1930:225).

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– No

Notes: "...the Hottentots have amongst them certain individuals who are specialists in the art of magic. Of these magicians, !gai aogu, we have extremely little information. Nothing at all appears to be

known about the method in which a person becomes a !gai aob, or of the training he has to undergo...The principal function of the !gai aob is to cure people who have been bewitched. He is considered as in some way connected with the /hei /nun—we are nowhere told how—and therefore has an immunity which ordinary people have not from the sickness caused by the /hei /nun or by their human agents, the witchcraft practitioners. This immunity he can impart to others, and so cure them of the disease, by inoculating them with his essence, as it were, which is contained in the dirt and perspiration of his body...As long as the !gai aob uses his powers in this way for good, he is much respected, and is an important person in the community. But he can also use it for evil, and by resorting to witchcraft make people ill or kill them, instead of curing them...It is difficult to determine what other regular functions the !gai aob has apart from the curing, or causing, of disease" (Schapera, 1930:389-391). "Some individuals played a dominant role in healing or rainmaking rituals, but it would be incorrect to view them as specialist religious practitioners. There is some mention of magicians, but very little is known of the methods they employed" (Boonzaier, 2010).

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

— No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of scriptures.

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

— No

Notes: According to Murdock and Wilson (1972; Column 6: Large or Impressive Structures), "there are no structures in the community that are appreciably larger or more impressive than the usual residential dwellings."

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

— No

Notes: According to Murdock and Wilson (1972; Column 6: Large or Impressive Structures), "there are no structures in the community that are appreciably larger or more impressive than the usual residential dwellings."

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that

some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: "The ghosts of the dead are known to the Naman by several names—most commonly as /hei /nun, 'fawn feet'; sometimes as /hei khoin, 'fawn-coloured people,' or sobo khoin, 'people of the shadow'; and also as //gaunagu" (Schapera, 1930:366).

Belief in afterlife:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: "The Hottentot beliefs concerning the fate of the dead have not been investigated in sufficient detail; and concrete information on the subject is contained only in a few fragmentary, but nevertheless important, observations. These leave untouched many problems which arise, and the following description cannot, therefore, be regarded as fully adequate. But it seems safe to say, in the light of the available information, that the Hottentots have no definite conception of an after-world or special land of the dead, nor is there any established theory of reincarnation. Olpp in a short sentence expresses concisely what appears to be the general Hottentot doctrine: 'They believe that the soul of a dead person goes with him into the grave, from which it has the faculty of emerging at will as a ghost, in either luminous or terrifying form.'" (Schapera, 1930:366).

Reincarnation in this world:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: "The Hottentot beliefs concerning the fate of the dead have not been investigated in sufficient detail; and concrete information on the subject is contained only in a few fragmentary, but nevertheless important, observations. These leave untouched many problems which arise, and the following description cannot, therefore, be regarded as fully adequate. But it seems safe to say, in the light of the available information, that the Hottentots have no definite conception of an after-world or special land of the dead, nor is there any established theory of reincarnation. Olpp in a short sentence expresses concisely what appears to be the general Hottentot doctrine: 'They believe that the soul of a dead person goes with him into the grave, from which it has the faculty of emerging at will as a ghost, in either luminous or terrifying form.'" (Schapera, 1930:366).

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Notes: "Dead people are as a rule disposed of by burial. The only other mode of disposal is exposure, which takes place only in a few special cases" (Schapera, 1930:358).

Cremation:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating the presence of cremation.

Mummification:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating the presence of mummification.

↳ Interment:

– Yes

Notes: "As soon as the body was brought out, they followed it in two separate groups to the place of burial, still lamenting and wailing. Here the body was stuck into the hole or lowered into the grave, and placed in a sitting position in the niche. The grave was then filled in with earth, and afterwards covered over with a heap of large stones and branches, so as to prevent wild animals from getting at the body" (Schapera, 1930:360).

↳ Corpse is flexed (legs are bent or body is crouched):

– Yes

Notes: Schapera, 1930:360

↳ Corpse is extended (lying flat on front or back):

– Yes

Notes: "According to Schultze, it is laid here flat on its back, with the grave itself on the right hand side and the head facing west" (Schapera, 1930:363). "I was only able to find out about burial customs. As they are maintained today, they are a mixture of old traditions, of Christian influences and of the progressive degeneration of the folk customs. The eyes of the corpse are closed, the body washed by old women and stretched out on its back. The arms are placed at the sides and the hands placed next each other in the lap with the back of the hand up. Skins are used as a shroud. They are wrapped around the body with the hairy side in and sprinkled with buchu powder and then sewn together. The face is kept uncovered until shortly before interment, then the tip of a skin that has been kept for the purpose is placed over it and sewed together loosely...The body, the burial of which I witnessed, was placed stretched out on its back. A squatting position is said to have been originally customary" (Schultze, Knight, and Ziolkowski, 1907:115).

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1900 CE - 1907 CE

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating the presence of cannibalism.

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– Yes

Notes: "Dead people are as a rule disposed of by burial. The only other mode of disposal is exposure, which takes place only in a few special cases. Among the Cape Hottentots, for example, one of twins might be buried alive, or else placed in some exposed spot or in bushes to be destroyed by the elements or by wild animals. Similarly, according to Hahn, 'a man who is killed as a criminal, or who is slain according to the rules of the vendetta, or a slave killed by the master, or enemies killed in the battle—all are left to the animals of the desert to be feasted upon, so that they will be entirely annihilated.' Such people who are devoured by vultures or hyenas are called //gauna //ora khoïn, i.e. people who died the //gauna death"

(Schapera, 1930:358-359).

↳ Feeding to animals:

– Yes

Notes: "Dead people are as a rule disposed of by burial. The only other mode of disposal is exposure, which takes place only in a few special cases. Among the Cape Hottentots, for example, one of twins might be buried alive, or else placed in some exposed spot or in bushes to be destroyed by the elements or by wild animals. Similarly, according to Hahn, 'a man who is killed as a criminal, or who is slain according to the rules of the vendetta, or a slave killed by the master, or enemies killed in the battle—all are left to the animals of the desert to be feasted upon, so that they will be entirely annihilated.' Such people who are devoured by vultures or hyenas are called //gauna //ora khoïn, i.e. people who died the //gauna death" (Schapera, 1930:358-359).

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating the presence of co-sacrifices.

Are grave goods present:

– No

Notes: "Apparently no objects of any kind were placed in or on the grave" (Schapera, 1930:360).

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Notes: "There were no special burial grounds or recognized grave-yards. Immediately after the death had taken place, the head of the kraal, with several of the men, went out to look for a suitable spot, where the grave was at once made. It took the form of a deep hole, in one side of which was hollowed out a special niche for the reception of the body. Sometimes they did not trouble to dig a grave, but selected a convenient cleft in a rock or the hole of some wild animal instead" (Schapera, 1930:360).

↳ In cemetery:

– No

Notes: "There were no special burial grounds or recognized grave-yards. Immediately after the death had taken place, the head of the kraal, with several of the men, went out to look for a suitable spot, where the grave was at once made. It took the form of a deep hole, in one side of which was hollowed out a special niche for the reception of the body. Sometimes they did not trouble to dig a grave, but selected a convenient cleft in a rock or the hole of some wild animal instead" (Schapera, 1930:360).

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of family tomb-crypts.

↳ Other formal burial type:

– Yes [specify]: Varying locations

Notes: "There were no special burial grounds or recognized grave-yards. Immediately after the death had taken place, the head of the kraal, with several of the men, went out to look for a suitable spot, where the grave was at once made. It took the form of a deep hole, in one side of which was hollowed out a special niche for the reception of the body. Sometimes they did not trouble to dig a grave, but selected a convenient cleft in a rock or the hole of some wild animal instead" (Schapera, 1930:360).

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: "Khoi have been under missionary influence for a considerable length of time, and relatively little information regarding religious beliefs is available. A range of myths that have been recorded shed some light on pre-Christian beliefs. Special significance was attached to the moon (it has been claimed that the Khoi 'worshipped' the moon) and to two central good beings, Tsûi-//goab (the deity) and Haiseb or Heitsi-eibib (the folk hero). The Khoi also believed in ghosts and witches..." (Boonzaier, 2010). There are limited ethnographic descriptions of pre-Christian Khoi beliefs. See questions below for available details.

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 238, High Gods [note: equivalent to Ethnographic Atlas column 34: High Gods], indicates that a high god is absent or not reported (Murdock, 1962-1971; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

Notes: "The ghosts of the dead are known to the Naman by several names—most commonly as /hei /nun, 'fawn feet'; sometimes as /hei khoi, 'fawn-coloured people,' or sobo khoi, 'people of the shadow'; and also as //gaunagu" (Schapera, 1930:366). "Neither Bushmen nor Hottentots, again, have any organized family or tribal ancestor worship, nor any form of religious practice in which the spirits of the dead are regularly invoked or propitiated, although among the Southern Bushmen as well as among the Hottentots dead people are occasionally prayed to" (Schapera, 1930:395).

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: "The people fear, he says, that the dead may return and molest them. For this

reason, when anybody has died, they all remove from the locality, believing that the dead person only haunts the place where he has died. Only if anything is taken from the hut of the dead person will his ghost follow them and trouble them" (Schapera, 1930:367). "Underlying this dread is the belief that the /hei /nun, the ghosts, cause most of the sickness and death, either in themselves, or through the lgei aogu, the magicians" (ibid, pg. 368). "...any change in weather, from calm to storm, from cold to heat, etc., is regarded as sent by the dead" (ibid, pg. 371).

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– Yes

Notes: "Often, when a man has died, he appears to a member of his family in sleep" (Schapera, 1930:368). "...the magicians are somehow in special contact with the ghosts, and consequently have the power to cure the illness caused by them" (Schapera, 1930:395).

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– I don't know

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Notes: "Often, when a man has died, he appears to a member of his family in sleep" (Schapera, 1930:368).

↳ In trance possession:

– I don't know

↳ Through divination processes:

– I don't know

↳ Only through specialists:

– Yes

Notes: "...the magicians are somehow in special contact with the ghosts, and consequently have the power to cure the illness caused by them" (Schapera, 1930:395).

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

Notes: No monarch is present.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– I don't know

Notes: A being with the name of Tsui//Goab is referenced (Schapera, 1930:382-386), but principal ethnographic authority (Schultze, Knight, and Ziolkowski, 1907:240) suspects this being to be identical with Haitsiaibeb (the folk-hero).

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: Haitsiaibena is a defied, legendary, folk hero among the Khoi. "Hai-tsi-ai-bena is the Hottentot name for the group of folk tales about a hero of former times, to whom, just a few decades ago, they still erected grave mounds in remote districts in the form of stone heaps upon which a passerby placed a stone or twig in the hope that he might be rewarded by finding a good path and water" (Schultze, Knight, and Ziolkowski, 1907:239).

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of supernatural monitoring among the Khoi.

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– No

Notes: Spirits of the dead are said to return and interfere with the living. However, it appears that the spirits are inherently mischievous/malicious, and not directly punishing the living for a specific reason or wrongdoing. "The people fear, he says, that the dead may return and molest them. For this reason, when anybody has died, they all remove from the locality, believing that the dead person only haunts the place where he has died. Only if anything is taken from the hut of the dead person will his ghost follow them and trouble them" (Schapera, 1930:367). "Underlying this dread is the belief that the /hei /nun, the ghosts, cause most of the sickness and death, either in themselves, or through the !gei aogu, the magicians" (ibid, pg. 368). "...any change in weather, from calm to storm, from cold to heat, etc., is regarded as sent by the dead" (ibid, pg. 371).

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence of supernatural beings bestowing rewards.

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of messianic beliefs.

Is an eschatology present:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of an eschatology.

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: "The sexual life of the Hottentots is no longer so strictly regulated as it seems to have been in the old days. There is now apparently great freedom of intercourse tolerated before and also practised after marriage. Formerly premarital unchastity was severely condemned among the Naman, and even penalized" (Schapera, 1930:241).

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: "Infidelity on the part of the husband is not recognized as a ground for divorce, nor is adultery on the part of the wife. In the old days, according to Kolb, the Cape Hottentots regarded the latter as a capital offence, punishable by death without further question and without the least regard for the status of the adulterer" (Schapera, 1930:252).

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of castration.

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of required fasting among the Khoi.

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Notes: "There is little information as the existence of food taboos among the Hottentots in more recent times. The only well-authenticated instance is in the case of the hare, which in all the tribes might be eaten only by women and children, and was strictly forbidden to men and to youths who had passed through the puberty rites. This taboo was apparently associated with the myth connecting the hare with the origin of death, which we have already met with among the Bushmen also. Even this restriction, however, seems now to have lapsed" (Schapera, 1930:239-240).

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of required sacrifice of time at regular meetings or prayers. "Neither Bushmen nor Hottentots, again, have any organized family or tribal ancestor worship, nor any form of religious practice in which the spirits of the dead are regularly invoked or propitiated, although among the Southern Bushmen as well as among the Hottentots dead people are occasionally prayed to" (Schapera, 1930:395).

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– Yes

Notes: The Khoi's most important rituals appear to be related to life-cycle events. Due to the importance of these events, participation is inferred to be required. "The central theme of virtually all Khoi ritual was the idea of transformation or transition from one status to another. Most rituals marked the critical periods of change in a person's life—birth, puberty, adulthood, marriage, and death. In all of these rituals, the concept of !nau was central. !nau was seen as a state of particular vulnerability and danger. The ceremonies all involved a period of seclusion associated with increased !nau. During these periods of social withdrawal, certain substances (notably water) were avoided, whereas others (such as fire or the buchu plant) were associated with protection. Of particular interest is the part played by livestock—not only in feasting associated with the rituals, but in the rituals themselves. In contrast with water, domestic stock seemed always to be associated with protection (e.g., feeding babies with the milk of cows or ewes, or the wearing of parts of a slaughtered animal, as in the case of female puberty rituals)" (Boonzaier, 2010).

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A chiefdom

Notes: SCCS Variable 237 (note: equivalent to EA column 33) Jurisdictional Hierarchy Beyond the Local Community indicates that the Nama have one level of political authority beyond the local community, which is indicative of a chiefdom (Murdock, 1962-1971; Retrieved from Divale, 2004). "Power within the tribal community at the time of my stay in Namaland, was, as it had been for generations, in the hands of a chief, gao`aob or *gao`b, a 'captain,' and of a council of older men, with whom the captain discussed all important matters...The right to sit in the council is not tied to specific conditions. Ability, experience and age qualify one. But in many particulars this ancient Hottentot form of government is today strongly influenced by the Cape Dutch models and Christian elements" (Schyltze, Knight, and Ziolkowski, 1907:120). "Each tribe was composed of a number of patrilineal clans (!hau !nati, lit. things within the tribe), i.e. groups of people claiming to be related in the male line. One of these clans claimed seniority, and the chieftainship of the whole tribe was hereditary in this senior clan, and inherited in the male line from father to son.... It appears from the clan names of the Gei //Khauan [tribe] that there must formerly have been several more clans in this tribe, so that on the whole the size of a clan cannot have been considerable...The various family groups which go together to form a clan are also called !hau !nati" (Schapera, 1930:225-226). "The clan was thus the strongest unit ever attained by the Naman. Time and again a powerful clan would go off on its own, asserting its independence of the others, and clan loyalty was always stronger than tribal loyalty. The chief of the tribe was little more than primus inter pares. He was acknowledged to be the head of the senior clan, and if a man of fine character was accorded a great deal of respect; but the heads of the other clans acted as his council, and he could not do much without their co-operation. The whole conduct of affairs in the tribe was—and still is—the concern of the older men" (Schapera, 1930:227). Due to the importance of ranked lineages, this entry considers the Khoi to be best described as a chiefdom.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 20 (Food Storage) indicates that no food storage is present (Murdock and Morrow, 1970; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 14, Routes of Land Transport, indicates that unimproved trails are used (Murdock and Morrow, 1970; Retrieved from Divale, 2004). Presumably, transportation infrastructure is not present.

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 14, Routes of Land Transport, indicates that unimproved trails are used (Murdock

and Morrow, 1970; Retrieved from Divale, 2004). Presumably, transportation infrastructure is not present.

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Notes: According to Tuden and Marshall (1972; column 10: police) "police functions are not specialized or institutionalized at any level of political integration, the maintenance of law and order being left exclusively to informal mechanisms of social control, to private retaliation, or to sorcery".

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– Yes

Notes: "Every large Hottentot kraal [community] had its own recognized headman or 'captain' (usually spoken of in the early Cape Records by the Dutch title 'kapitein'), whose status was hereditary in the same way as that of the chief. The ceremonies of accession, as described by Kolb, were also similar to those of the chief, except that the headman had to make his pledge before the adult men of the kraal, and to provide the feast for them. All these men constituted a loosely-organized council over which he presided. They acted in the first instance as a court of justice. They met to settle disputes of right and property between the inhabitants of the kraal, and tried and punished criminal offences committed within their jurisdiction. The verdict arrived at was pronounced by the headman, and where the death penalty was imposed his was the first hand to smite down the culprit. There was no appeal from their decision or sentence to the main tribal council" (Schapera, 1930:329).

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Notes: "These rules are not formulated in any legal code. Some of them have come into being as decisions of the tribal council in judicial trials, while in more recent times others have even been deliberately enacted, as for example in the case of the various proclamations issued by such chiefs as Hendrik Witbooi. Legislation of the latter type, however, does not appear to have occurred in the original conditions of Hottentot life. The laws of the Hottentots are to a very considerable extent inherent in the social organization and usages of the people. They have developed as a result of the more or less unconscious adjustment of personal relations, as a product of economic activities, and so on, and have become accepted as norms or standards of life and conduct which are binding as such on the community. Their existence, in other words, is derived from the authority of tradition and precedents" (Schapera, 1930:337).

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Notes: The Khoi are pastoralists, with a secondary dependence on hunting. Source of information: Ethnographic Atlas (Murdock, 1962-1971), retrieved from Divale, 2004; Variables 203-207, 232.

↳ Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Hunting (including marine animals)

– Pastoralism

Notes: The Khoi are pastoralists, with a secondary dependence on hunting. Source of information: Ethnographic Atlas (Murdock, 1962-1971), retrieved from Divale, 2004; Variables 203-207, 232.